

Some studies on nucleation, crystallization and microstructural behaviour of mica glass-ceramics in the system $0.8\text{BaO}\cdot 0.2\text{K}_2\text{O}\cdot 0.4\text{MgO}\cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot 6\text{SiO}_2\cdot 2\text{MgF}_2$

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Abstract : Glass-ceramics containing barium fluorophlogopite as a main crystal phase based on the system $0.8\text{BaO}\cdot 0.2\text{K}_2\text{O}\cdot 0.4\text{MgO}\cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot 6\text{SiO}_2\cdot 2\text{MgF}_2$ was investigated with respect to phase separation, nucleation and crystallization by Differential thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The glass transition temperature (T_g) and two distinct crystallization peak temperatures were observed in DTA curve. The crystallization kinetics of glass-ceramics was also studied. Avrami exponent and activation energy for the first peak crystallization temperature (T_p^1) were 2.7 and 226.3 ± 3 kJ/mol and the corresponding values for second peak crystallization temperature (T_p^2) were 3.7 and 322.6 ± 3 kJ/mol.

Keywords : Glass-ceramics, ceramics, X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscope.

Introduction

The glass-ceramics, a polycrystalline material composed of at least one crystalline phase dispersed in a vitreous matrix, is produced by the controlled crystallization of highly viscous glass-forming melts. The transition occurs from 'vitreous to crystalline' in glass-ceramics via two kinds of transformation-nucleation and crystal growth. The first one is an endothermic process and the second one is an exothermic process¹. The two dimensional mica crystals are nucleated internally and crystallized from fluorine containing glasses. The most unique feature of mica glass-ceramics is that they can be machined to precise tolerances and surface finish with conventional metal working tools²⁻⁴. Mica glass-ceramics, particularly phlogopite system, have excellent machinability due to the layered lattice structure of the sheet silicates arranged in a 'house of cards' microstructures, which causes a perfect basal cleavage along the (001) planes of mica crystals. Besides above, they possess higher strength, fracture toughness, thermal shock resistance, and have excellent dielectric properties.

Glass-ceramics based on alkaline earth fluorophlogopites, particularly barium fluorophlogopite, are claimed

to have two to three times higher mechanical strength than the corresponding potassium fluorophlogopite glass-ceramics⁶⁻⁸.

Beall² undertook the first study of the alkaline earth fluor mica glass-ceramics, later on Hoda and Beall⁵ investigated glasses of different compositions containing barium, calcium and strontium based on fluorophlogopite stoichiometry. Most of the compositions were susceptible to crystallization during casting.

Recently Uno *et al.*⁶ observed glasses from the ternary system $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)\text{-Ba}_{0.5}\text{Mg}_3(\text{Al}\cdot\text{Si}_3\cdot\text{O}_{10})\text{F}_2\text{-Mg}_2\text{Al}_4\text{Si}_5\text{O}_{18}$. The detail compositions were not given, however it was stated that the compositions were close to $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{Mg}_3(\text{Al}\cdot\text{Si}_3\cdot\text{O}_{10})\text{F}_2$ stoichiometry. They clearly indicated the improved strengths and fracture toughness values.

Gregg *et al.*⁹ investigated microstructural development in one composition from the $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)\text{-Ba}_{0.5}\text{Mg}_3(\text{Al}\cdot\text{Si}_3\cdot\text{O}_{10})\text{F}_2\text{-Mg}_2\text{Al}_4\text{Si}_5\text{O}_{18}$ system as a part of a US NIH programme towards developing CAD/CAM dental ceramics.

Henry *et al.*¹⁰ observed nucleation and crystallization

behavior based on $8\text{SiO}_2 \cdot Y\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 4\text{MgO} \cdot 2\text{MgF}_2 \cdot \text{BaO}$ where the varying of aluminum oxide ($Y = 1.5\text{--}3.0$). They clearly indicated the reducing the alumina content reduces the glass transition temperature, first peak crystallization temperature and promotes bulk crystal nucleation. The first peak was corresponding to barium fluorophlogopite. High alumina contents favoured the formation of cordierite, mullite and barium aluminum silicate.

Henry *et al.*¹¹ observed microstructure, hardness and machinability based on $8\text{SiO}_2 \cdot Y\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 4\text{MgO} \cdot 2\text{MgF}_2 \cdot \text{BaO}$ where the varying of aluminum oxide ($Y = 1.5\text{--}3.0$). They found hardness and machinability to be highly dependent on the formation of an interconnected house of cards microstructure.

However, to our knowledge, no previous attempt has been made to study the nucleation, crystallization, growth, strength and machinability by partially replacing barium with potassium in barium fluor mica glass-ceramics.

In the present investigation, we have studied the nucleation and crystallization behavior of the glass obtained by substituting 0.1 mole BaO with 0.1 mole K_2O in the system $\text{BaO} \cdot 4\text{MgO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 6\text{SiO}_2 \cdot 2\text{MgF}_2$.

Experimental

Parent glass preparation :

The glass batches having weight-percentage compositions of BaCO_3 , K_2CO_3 , SiO_2 , MgO , Al_2O_3 and MgF_2 were prepared (Table 1). These materials were of high purity and analytical grade reagents. The glass batches

Table 1. Chemical composition of the glass

BaCO_3	K_2CO_3	MgO	Al_2O_3	SiO_2	MgF_2
17.914	3.174	18.679	111.694	40.52	14.285

were properly mixed in an attrition mill, thereafter melted in a platinum crucible for 4–5 h in an electrically heated furnace operating at 1450–1500 °C. The melt was poured into a hot iron mould to make glass block of about $60 \times 25 \times 10$ mm dimension. After releasing from the mould, the glass block was immediately transferred to an annealing furnace operating at 650 °C and soaked for 1 h followed by natural cooling to room temperature.

After annealing, the block was cut into pieces to about 1–2 mm thickness with the help of a precision low speed

cutting machine (Buehler). These cut samples were fired at 710 °C for 2 h for nucleation. This nucleation temperature was determined by DTA study. The samples after nucleation heated to the corresponding crystallization temperature at a rate of 2 °C/min and the samples were kept at the crystallization temperatures for 5 h.

Characterization techniques :

Differential thermal analysis (DTA) :

Differential thermal analysis (DTA) was done using Shimadzu DT40 thermal analyzer with α -alumina powder as a reference material. The glass was crushed and finally ground to $\sim 75 \mu\text{m}$ suitable for DTA analysis. Non-isothermal experiments were performed by heating ~ 17 mg glass sample, crystallized at different temperatures, at a heating rate of 5, 10, 15 and 20 °C/min in the temperature range from ambient to 1000 °C. Differential thermal analysis (DTA) procedure was applied to calculate the value of activation energy by Ozawa equation and the corresponding Avrami exponent was calculated by Augis-Bennet equation.

X-Ray powder diffraction (XRD) :

X-Ray powder diffraction was carried out for the heat treated samples at different crystallization temperatures. All samples were heat treated using a heating rate of 10 °C/min to the nucleation temperature of 710 °C, soaked for 2 h at this temperature and heated again at 2 °C/min to the corresponding crystallization temperature. The samples were kept at the crystallization temperature for 5 h followed by natural cooling to room temperature. The ceramised glass samples were ground to $\sim 75 \mu\text{m}$. XRD experiments were performed using X-ray powder diffractometer (PW 1830, Panalytical) using Ni filtered $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$, X-radiation with scanning speed of 2° (2 θ) per minute. The diffraction pattern was recorded within Bragg's angle ranges $5^\circ < 2\theta < 70^\circ$. The phases were identified by JCPDS numbers (ICDD-PDF₂ data base).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) :

Different samples from all the crystallization temperature (heating schedule as mentioned earlier) were studied to investigate the micro structural development with back scattered electron imaging (BEI) mode in a Hitachi, S3400N, Japan, scanning electron microscope. Before study, surface of all the samples were polished by following standard procedures and finally with diamond paste.

The polished samples were etched chemically by HF solution for 30 s.

Density :

The densities of all the crystallized samples at different temperatures were measured by water displacement method following Archimedes principle.

Results and discussion

Characterization of DTA peaks :

Two well-defined exothermic peaks are visible in all the DTA thermograms. When the glass sample was heated at 10 °C/min, the 1st peak appeared at 793 °C and the 2nd peak appeared at 894 °C (Fig. 1). To characterize the peaks, the powdered sample (grading same as that used for DTA analysis) was heated separately to the cor-

Fig. 1. Differential thermal analysis plots of glass samples of varying heating rate : (1) 5 °C/min, (2) 10 °C/min, (3) 15 °C/min, (4) 20 °C/min.

responding peak temperatures at a rate of 10 °C/min (same as that of DTA) in an electrically heated furnace and the samples then air-quenched at the room temperature supposing complete arrest of any further phase changes during quenching. XRD study was done to identify the different phases formed in the heat treated samples under consideration. It is clear from the study that the first exothermic peak temperature corresponds to the formation of K-fluorophlogopite and the second one corresponds to the formation of Ba-fluorophlogopite (Fig. 2).

Kinetics of crystallization :

DTA curves for glass samples at a heating rate of 5,

Fig. 2. X-Ray diffraction patterns of glass samples for the corresponding DTA peak temperatures, heating rate 10 °C/min [B-Barium fluorophlogopite, K-Potassium fluorophlogopite].

10, 15 and 20 °C/min are shown in Fig. 1. Two well-defined crystallization peaks are visible in all the DTA thermograms. Moreover, it is clear from these curves that the two distinct crystallization peak temperatures shifted towards right with increasing heating rate. The nucleation and crystallization temperature were determined from DTA analysis of the glass sample.

The kinetics of glass crystallization is studied on the basis of the Johnson-Mehl-Avrami (JMA) equation¹²⁻¹⁹.

$$X = 1 - \exp [-(kt)^n] \tag{1}$$

where X is the fraction crystallized at a given temperature; k is the reaction rate constant and n is the Avrami exponent, which is a dimensionless factor depending on the nucleation process and growth morphology.

From Johnson-Mehl-Avrami equation, non-isothermal crystallization kinetics of glass can be described by the Ozawa equation²⁰.

Ozawa equation is given below

$$\ln \beta = - \frac{E}{RT_p} + C \tag{2}$$

The activation energy (E) was obtained from the relation between the heating rate (β) and maximum crystallization peak temperature (T_p) in the exothermic peak of the DTA curve, where β is the heating rate, R is the universal gas constant. As shown in Table 2 and Figs. 3 and 4.

Table 2. The values of crystallization peak temperature at different heating rates

Heating rate, β	T_p^1 (°C)	T_p^2 (°C)
15	775	882
10	793	894
15	801	902
20	809	907

Fig. 3. Ozawa plot of $\ln \beta$ and $1/T_p$ at 1st crystallization peak temperature (T_p^1).

Fig. 4. Ozawa plot of $\ln \beta$ and $1/T$ at 2nd crystallization peak temperature (T_p^2).

In Ozawa equation, the slope of the plot of $\ln \beta$ vs $1/T_p$ is equal to $-E/R$.

From Augis-Bennett equation²¹, the value of Avrami exponent (n) can be estimated using the value of activa-

tion energy.

$$n = \frac{2.5}{\Delta T} \times \frac{RT_p^2}{E} \quad (3)$$

where, ΔT is the full width of the exothermic peak at the half-maximum intensity, n is the Avrami exponent or crystallization index, i.e. Avrami exponent depends upon the actual nucleation and growth mechanism.

The activation energy and Avrami exponent were calculated using the above equations and shown in Table 3. From 1st crystallization peak temperature, Avrami expo-

Table 3. Kinetic parameters of crystallization

Crystallization peak temperature	Activation energy (Ozawa) kJ/mol	Avrami exponent
T_p^1	226.3 ± 3	2.7
T_p^2	322.6 ± 3	3.7

T_p^1 = 1st crystallization peak temperature.
 T_p^2 = 2nd crystallization peak temperature.

nent was found to be 2.7, which is close to 3; therefore the fact indicates that bulk nucleation and two dimensional growth occurs for the glass-ceramics. From 2nd crystallization peak temperature, Avrami exponent was found to be 3.7, which is close to 4, therefore the fact indicates that it is a case of bulk nucleation and three dimensional crystal growths for the material concerned²²⁻²⁵.

Results of X-ray diffraction :

Various crystal phases were identified by JCPDS reference file presented in Table 4.

Table 4. List of JCPDS files to used to identify the main crystal phase formations observed

Crystal phase	JCPDS reference file
Barium fluorophlogopite [BaMg ₃ AlSi ₃ O ₁₀ F ₂]-B	00-019-0117
Potassium fluorophlogopite [KMg ₃ AlSi ₃ O ₁₀ F ₂]-K	01-076-0816
Alpha-hexacelsian [Ba _{0.808} (Al _{1.71} Si _{2.29})O ₈]-H	01-088-1050
Enstatite [MgSiO ₃]-E	00-002-0546

At 800 °C, peaks of K-fluorophlogopite appeared at 27° (2θ) and 34° (2θ) as a major component whereas, Ba-fluorophlogopite appeared as a minor component (Fig. 5). The formation of Ba-fluorophlogopite at 800 °C seems to be unusual which is against the observation made during the DTA analysis. But the formation of Ba-fluorophlogopite might be due to the long duration of

Fig. 5. XRD patterns for glass samples at different crystallization temperatures [B-Barium fluorophlogopite, K-Potassium fluorophlogopite, H-Alpha-hexacelsian and E-Enstatite]

soaking at this crystallization temperature. At 900 °C, four new peaks of barium aluminum silicate (alpha-hexacelsian) at 11°, 22°, 30° and 54° (2θ) and one new peak of enstatite 28° (2θ) appeared along with Ba-fluorophlogopite and K-fluorophlogopite. From 900 °C to 1000 °C there are no changes in the intensity of the peaks except, one new peak of K-fluorophlogopite at 18° (2θ) appeared. From 1000 °C to 1100 °C there are no changes in the intensity of the peaks but one new peak of enstatite at 63° (2θ) appeared. At 1100 °C and 1150 °C, the sharpness of the peaks of both barium aluminum silicate (alpha-hexacelsian) and enstatite have been increased. With increasing heat treatment temperature, the sharpness of the barium aluminum silicate (alpha-hexacelsian) is increased. This might be the indication that partial decomposition of Ba-fluorophlogopite into barium aluminum silicate (alpha-hexacelsian) and enstatite. This decomposition is not visible in the DTA scan up to 1000 °C. This decomposition might be co-related to some extent to the changes in Avrami exponent (*n*) from 3 to 4, where monoclinic crystal structure is converted to hexagonal crystal structure. Even after this, it is needless to mention that Ba-fluorophlogopite and K-fluorophlogopite along with barium aluminum silicate (alpha-hexacelsian) phases are the major phases formed in all the samples crystallized at higher temperature.

Microstructure analysis :

Samples heated at 800 °C for five hours exhibit very

fine submicron microstructures consists of some blocky crystal (Fig. 6a). After increasing heat treatment temperature through 900 °C to 1000 °C for five hours, exhibited a large number of slightly bigger blocky crystals (Figs. 6b and 6c) compared to that of at 800 °C These blocky crystals are dense and appeared white in the back scattered electron micrographs.

Fig. 6a. SEM photographs of polished and etched surface of samples nucleated at 710 °C for 2 h and ceramised for 5 h at 800 °C

Fig. 6b. SEM photographs of polished and etched surface of samples nucleated at 710 °C for 2 h and ceramised for 5 h at 900 °C

Sample heated at 1100 °C for five hour exhibit the appearance of smaller crystals with acicular morphology (Fig. 6d). But when the sample is heated at 1150 °C for five hours, exhibit the development of large sized crystals with acicular morphology and forms “house of cards” structures (Fig. 6e).

Fig. 6c. SEM photographs of polished and etched surface of samples nucleated at 710 °C for 2 h and ceramised for 5 h at 1000 °C.

Fig. 6d. SEM photographs of polished and etched surface of samples nucleated at 710 °C for 2 h and ceramised for 5 h at 1100 °C.

Fig. 6e. SEM photographs of polished and etched surface of samples nucleated at 710 °C for 2 h and ceramised for 5 h at 1150 °C.

The appearance of blocky crystals might be due to the formation of mica booklets and in many cases have an aspect ratio of < 1 . As the temperature further increased, the number of crystal per unit volume decreased and aspect ratio of the crystal increased (Figs. 6a-c). It might be due to the dissolution of crystals with an aspect ratio of < 1 and reprecipitation of constituents onto those crystal of higher aspect ratio. This energetically unfavorable configuration might therefore be the driving force towards attaining the long crystal observed after treatment of five hours at 1100 °C and 1150 °C (Figs. 6d and 6e), which is discussed elsewhere⁹.

It is quite clear from the SEM micrographs at 1100 °C and 1150 °C that a few cracks appeared during crystallization. Some cracks are intercrystalline and some are transcrystalline in nature.

Physical properties :

Density of as-prepared glass was about 2.98 g/cm³. The density changes of the glass-ceramic samples heat treated at 800–1150 °C for five hours are shown in Fig. 7. Density achieves the maximum value at 1100 °C, beyond this the density decreased with increasing heat

Fig. 7. Variation of bulk density of glass samples against different crystallization temperatures.

treatment temperature. This decrease in density may be attributed to the partial decomposition of barium fluorophlogopite into barium aluminium silicate (alpha hexacelsian), which may be co-related to the XRD observations. This observation suggests that the stability of barium fluorophlogopite at lower temperatures is better

than that at higher temperatures. The findings are similar to the observations made by Radonjic²⁶.

Furthermore, the density at higher temperature i.e. at 1150 °C reduced substantially due to the formation of cracks in the crystallized materials, which is also clearly visible from the SEM micrographs.

Conclusions :

(i) The heat treatment conditions for nucleation at 710 °C for two hours and crystallization at different temperatures at 800, 900 and at 1000 °C for five hours can obtain fine structured glass-ceramics. Crystallization for five hours at 1100 °C and 1150 °C can be used to obtain mica crystals of higher aspect ratio and “house of cards” structure.

(ii) The activation energy of 1st peak of crystallization temperature and 2nd peak of crystallization temperature were 226.3 ± 3 and 322.6 ± 3 kJ/mol respectively. The Avrami exponent was determined to be 2.7 for 1st peak of crystallization temperature, which indicate that bulk nucleation and two dimensional growths occur in the glass-ceramics. Similarly, the Avrami exponent was determined to be 3.7 for 2nd peak of crystallization temperature, which indicates that it is a case of bulk nucleation and three dimensional crystal growths for the material concerned.

(iii) From XRD patterns, it can be concluded that at lower temperatures Ba-fluorophlogopite and K-fluorophlogopite are the major phases in the glass-ceramics. With increasing heat treatment temperature, the major phases are partially decomposes to other phases viz. barium aluminum silicate (alpha-hexacelsian) and enstatite.

(iv) It is clear from the findings that when potassium and barium is added in the above mentioned system, both the micas i.e. K-fluorophlogopite and Ba-fluorophlogopite are formed simultaneously.

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